

DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION AND *IN SILICO* STUDIES OF SOME NOVEL 3-SUBSTITUTED- 5-([1,1'-BIPHENYL]-4-YL METHYLENE) THIAZOLIDINE 2,4-DIONE DERIVATIVES AS ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

P. LAXMI MADHURI¹, G. RAJITHA^{2*}

¹*Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Maissammaguda, Dhulapally
(Post Via Hakimpet), Secunderabad Telangana- 500100, India.*

²*Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology, Sri Padmavati Mahila Visvavidyalayam,
Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh -517502, India*

Abstract

A series of novel 3-substituted- 5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene) thiazolidine-2,4-diones were synthesised by the reaction of 5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene) thiazolidine-2,4-diones with aryl/alkyl halides. The structures of the synthesized compounds were characterized using IR, NMR, and Mass spectroscopy. All the synthesized compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antioxidant activity using DPPH free radical scavenging and H₂O₂ assay methods. The *in-silico* antidiabetic activity was carried out at the PPAR γ receptor (PDB ID:2PRG) with pioglitazone as a standard. The antioxidant activity showed that compounds A3, A4, A5, A6, and A8 with bulky substituents exhibited significant activity when compared to ascorbic acid. All the synthesized compounds obeyed Lipinski's rule of five and showed good oral absorption. Molecular docking studies revealed that some compounds exhibited significant G scores than pioglitazone and from the prime MM-GB/SA studies, it was further confirmed that the compound A6 exhibited significant binding affinity with the PPAR γ receptor than pioglitazone.

Keywords: Thiazolidinediones, PPAR γ , DPPH, antidiabetic, antioxidant, *insilico*

Introduction:

Thiazolidinedione is a well-known chemical entity containing an active methylene group at the 5th position [1]. Thiazolidinediones are reported to have diversified activities like antioxidant, antidiabetic, antihyperlipidemic, and many others [2]. Diabetes mellitus type II is an evident metabolic disorder arising because of a lack of insulin production/insulin resistance or both [3]. The increasing prevalence of diabetes in the world's population and deaths reported because of the complications arising from it are worrying [4]. It is evident from recent studies that oxidative stress plays a pivotal role in the precipitation of chronic disorders like cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, etc [5]. Thiazolidinediones are indicated in the treatment of diabetes mellitus type II by interacting at the peroxisome proliferated activated receptor (PPAR) γ receptor [6]. Pioglitazone and rosiglitazone are some of the marketed drugs for the treatment of diabetes mellitus. Their use as antidiabetics is confined due to the concerns over weight gain, and dysfunction of heart & kidneys [7]. Therefore, there is an urge to develop novel thiazolidinediones with fewer side effects having both antidiabetic and antioxidant activity. Biphenyls are moieties with multifunctional activities like antioxidant [8], antidiabetic [9], antihyperlipidemic [10], and many others [11]. Combining thiazolidinediones with biphenyls might lead to compounds with both antioxidant and antidiabetic activity. 5-substituted-2,4-thiazolidinediones are prepared by reacting aldehydes with thiazolidinediones by Knoevenagel condensation reaction. Hence, the current study aims to design and synthesize series of novel 5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene) thiazolidine-2,4-diones, characterize their structure by IR, NMR, and Mass spectra, evaluate their *in vitro* antioxidant activity, perform *in silico* antidiabetic activity at the PPAR γ receptors by molecular docking and to predict the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) properties of the drugs.

Materials and methods

All the chemicals and solvents used in the present study were purchased from Merck, Sd Fine Chemicals Limited, and Sigma Aldrich USA. Melting points were determined by a digital melting point apparatus and remained uncorrected. For the monitoring of the progress of the reaction, pre-coated TLC plates (Silica gel 60 F254 plates from Merck, Germany) were used. The spots were developed using an iodine chamber and observed under a UV lamp. Shimadzu UV Visible double spectrophotometer and UV probe 2.71 software was used. IR spectra (KBr discs) were confirmed by Perkin Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr pellets technique.

^1H NMR and ^{13}C were recorded on Bruker 500 MHz NMR spectrophotometer using CDCl_3 and DMSO as the solvent. Mass spectra were recorded on the Shimadzu mass spectrophotometer.

Chemistry

Initially, biphenyl carbaldehyde (3.2mmol) and 2,4-thiazolidinedione (3.2mmol) were taken in a round-bottomed flask. 20 ml of ethanol and a catalytic amount of piperidine (0.5ml) were added to the above solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 19 hrs and cooled to room temperature. The solid precipitated (A1) was filtered and washed with cold water. The product is purified by recrystallization using ethanol as a solvent. Later 5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene) thiazolidine-2,4-dione (A1) (0.02 mmol) and substituted alkyl/aryl chlorides (0.02 mmol) were taken in a round-bottomed flask. To this mixture sodium hydroxide (0.02 mmol) in 20ml ethanol: water (1:1) solution was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 18-20 hrs^[12,13] (Scheme 1). The product crystallized out upon cooling. The progress of the reaction was monitored through TLC using ethyl acetate and ether (4:6). The products were purified by recrystallization using ethanol.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of 3-substituted-5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene)-1,3- thiazolidine-2,4-dione (A1-A9)

Step I

Step II

PHYSICOCHEMICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS A1-A9

Compound A1: 5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene)-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ Yield: 78 R_f : 0.72 FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3223 cm^{-1} (N-H), 3034 cm^{-1} (Ar-H), 1698 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1431 cm^{-1} (C=C), 1330 cm^{-1} (C-N), 750 cm^{-1} (C-S); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 10.96 (s, 1H, NH), 7.97 (s, 1H, HC=C), 7.6-7.42 (m, 5H, Ar-H) ppm; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 282 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

Compound A2: 3-methyl-5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene)-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ Yield: 71.2 R_f : 0.69 FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3010 cm^{-1} (Ar-H), 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1470 cm^{-1} (C=C), 1310 cm^{-1} (C-N), 750 cm^{-1} (C-S); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.95 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.72-7.41 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 3.27 (s, 3H, CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 167.96 (C=O), 166.53 (C=O), 143-127.08 (Ar-C), 121.9 (C-S), 27.96 (CH_3) ppm. Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 296.30 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

Compound A3: 3-(3,5-dimethoxybenzyl)-5-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl methylene)-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$ Yield: 62 R_f : 0.9 FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 2940 cm^{-1} (Ar-H), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1450 cm^{-1} (C=C), 1330 cm^{-1} (C-N), 1270 cm^{-1} (C-O), 750 cm^{-1} (C-S); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.94 (s, 1H, HC=C), 7.72-7.38 (m, 10 H, Ar-H), 6.59 (m, 2H, HC-C-O), 4.85 (s, 2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C-N}$), 3.79 (s, 6H, OCH_3) ppm. ^{13}C

NMR(500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 169.05 (C=O), 168.07 (C=O), 155.17 (ArC-O), 152.19 (Ar C-O), 148.55 (C=C-CH-), 133.59 - 127.12 (Ar C), 121.1 (C-S), 106.69 (O-C-CH Ar), 100.16 (O-C-CH), 55.39 (C-O), 45.19 (CH₂) ppm; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 432.10 [M+1]⁺.

Compound A4: ethyl {(5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl]methylidene)-2,4-dioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl}acetate

C₂₀H₁₇NO₄S Yield: 83.3 R_f: 0.89 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 2910 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1734 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1683 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1637 cm⁻¹ (C=O ester), 1355 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 1190 cm⁻¹ (C=C), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.98 (s, 1H, HC=), 7.74 - 7.26 (m, n9H, Ar.-H), 4.50 (s, 2H, CH₂-N), 4.26 (q, 2H, CH₂-O), 1.31 (t, 3H, CH₃) ppm; ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 177.08 (C=O ester), 169.00 (C=O), 165.59 (C=O), 143-127.15 (ArC), 121.9 (C-S), 62.19 (CH₂ ester), 42.17 (CH₂-N), 14.11 (CH₃) ppm; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 369 [M+2]⁺.

Compound A5: 5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl]methylidene]-3-[(pyridin-3-yl)methyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

C₂₂H₁₆N₂O₂S Yield: 73 R_f: 0.8 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3010 cm⁻¹ (ArH), 2970 cm⁻¹ (HC), 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1360 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 1190 cm⁻¹ (C=C), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 8.74 (d, 1H, HC-N), 8.58 (t, 1H, -HC-N), 7.96 (d, 1H, HC=C), 7.8- 7.28 (m, 11H, Ar-H), 4.93 (s, 2H, CH₂) ppm; ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 166.07 (C=O), 168.09 (C=O), 150.55 (C-N), 149.88 (C-N), 139.28 - 123.97 (Ar C), 121.1 (C=C), 42.88 (CH₂) ppm; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 373 [M+1]⁺.

Compound A6 :5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl methylene]-3-[-((2'-cyano)-1,1'-biphenyl-4-yl)methyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

C₃₀H₂₀N₂O₂S Yield: 76 R_f: 0.8 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3030 cm⁻¹ (Ar HC=C), 2920 cm⁻¹ (CH₂), 2220 cm⁻¹ (CN), 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1360 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 1200 cm⁻¹ (C=C), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.97 (s, 1H, HC=), 7.76-7.46 (m, 17H, Ar.-H), 4.98 (s, 2H, CH₂) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 168.08 (C=O), 166.45 (C=O), 133 - 127 (Ar-C), 121.01 (C-S), 118 (CN), 111.47 (C-CN), 44.91 (CH₂) ppm ; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 473 [M+1]⁺.

Compound A7: (5Z)-5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl]methylidene]-3-pentyl-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

C₂₁H₂₁NO₂S Yield: 85.3 R_f: 0.66 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3050 cm⁻¹ (ArH C=C), 2970 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1320 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.93 (s, 1H, HC=C), 7.73 - 7.37 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 3.75 (t, 2H, N-CH₂), 1.67 (d, 2H, CH₂-C-N), 1.55-1.27 (m, 4H, CH₂) 0.88-0.86 (t, 3H, CH₃) ppm; ¹³C NMR(500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 177.87 (C=O), 170.82 (C=O), 143.22 - 126 (Ar-C), 121.9 (C-S), 42.91 (CH₂-N), 29.08 - 22.67 (aliphatic C) ppm ; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 351 [M]⁺.

Compound A8: (5E)-5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl]methylidene]-3-(6-hydroxyhexyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

C₂₂H₂₃NO₃S Yield: 88 R_f: 0.8 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3350 cm⁻¹ (OH), 3030 cm⁻¹ (ArH C=C), 2940 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1380 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 1080 cm⁻¹ (C-O), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.93 (s, 1H, HC=C), 7.89 - 7.26 (m, 9H, Ar.-H), 3.80 (t, 2H, O-CH₂), 3.75 (t, 2H, N-CH₂), 1.73 (m, 2H, CH₂-C-O), 1.59-1.25 (m, 6H, CH₂) ppm; ¹³C NMR(500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 177.87 (C=O), 170.82 (C=O), 143.22 - 126 (Ar-C), 121.9 (C-S), 42.91 (CH₂-N), 29.08 - 22.67 (aliphatic C) ppm; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 351 [M]⁺. 381 [M+1]⁺.

Compound A9: (5E)-5-[(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl]methylidene]-3-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-2,4-dione

C₁₉H₁₃NO₂S Yield: 75 R_f: 0.69 FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3250 cm⁻¹ (HC \equiv CH), 2920 cm⁻¹ (CH₂), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1330 cm⁻¹ (C-N), 1180 cm⁻¹ (HC=C), 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.99 (s, 1H, HC=C), 7.74 - 7.38 (m, 9H, Ar.-H), 4.53 - 4.52 (s, 2H, N-CH₂), 2.29 (s, 1H, HC \equiv) ppm; ¹³C NMR(500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 168.02 (C=O), 166.09 (C=O), 143-127 (Ar-C), 120.64 (C-S), 76.09(C \equiv), 76.09 (\equiv C), 30.71 (CH₂) ppm ; Mass spectrum (ESI): m/z 320.10 [M+1]⁺.

Biological studies

Antioxidant activity

Interaction with stable free radical DPPH^[14]

The 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging assay was done based on the reported protocols from the literature ^[15,16]. A 0.1 mmol ethanolic DPPH solution was prepared and 2.4 ml of this solution was added with 1.6 ml of the 0.1 mmol sample solution. The reaction mixture was mixed well and kept in the dark for 30 min. The absorbance of the mixture was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at 517 nm. Ethanol is used as the blank and Ascorbic acid is the standard. The percentage inhibition of the DPPH free radical is calculated using the formula :

$$\text{Percentage(\%)} \text{ inhibition} = (\text{A}_o - \text{A}_s) / \text{A}_o \times 100$$

Where A_o - Absorbance of the control

A_s - Absorbance of the sample/ standard

Assay of Hydrogen peroxide Scavenging Activity^[17]

The hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity was determined by the methods reported in the literature ^[18]. A 4 mmol solution of hydrogen peroxide was prepared in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4). The hydrogen peroxide concentration was determined spectrophotometrically at 230 nm. 1 ml of different samples at 0.1mM concentration were added to 0.6 ml hydrogen peroxide – PBS solution. After 10 min, the absorbance of H₂O₂ and samples were determined at 230 nm using phosphate buffer saline as a blank. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard. The percentage inhibition of H₂O₂ is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)Scavenged [H}_2\text{O}_2\text{]} = (\text{A}_o - \text{A}_s)/\text{A}_o \times 100$$

Where A_o - Absorbance of the control

A_s- Absorbance of the sample/ standard

In silico studies

The design and development of new drugs involve a variety of challenges which may be the binding ability, the physicochemical properties of drugs, cost, time, and demand. Thus, it is imperative to refine the design of the drugs to ensure major success. One of the eminent causes for the rejection of drug candidates seems to be their poor absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) properties ^[19]. The *in-silico* ADME studies were conducted for the described (A1-A9) compounds by using the QikProp module of the Schrodinger suite 2021. The prepared ligands were studied for their ADME properties like molecular weight, total solvent accessible surface areas, number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, oral absorption, log P values, and violations of the rule of five. Lipinski's rule of five is followed for the prediction of the drug likeliness. If a molecule is not obeying any two of the parameters, then it is less likely to become a drug.

Molecular docking

Molecular modeling and docking help to understand the interaction between the ligand and the receptor. It helps in predicting the binding affinity of the molecules at the receptors so that researchers can analyze and develop more efficient lead candidates. ^[20,21]. molecular docking involves the following steps:

I)Preparation of the protein

The structure of the ternary complex of the PPAR γ cocrystallized with rosiglitazone (PDB ID:2PRG) retrieved from the protein data bank (PDB) was used as the initial structure ^[22]. The protein structure was prepared using the Schrodinger suite 2021-4 protein preparations wizard module. It contains three chains A, B, and C complexed with the known agonist rosiglitazone. Since a completely determined and continuous chain was desired, chain A was selected for the present study ^[23]. The protein size has been minimized using the optimized potentials for simulations-3 (OPLS-3) molecular force field, with the RMSD of the crystallographic atom set at 0.3 Å°.

II) Generation of the Grid box

Using the G-module of the Schrodinger suite 2021-4 in extra precision (XP) mode A grid box was generated to define the active site.

III) Preparation of the ligand

The structures in 2D were generated and optimized using the LigPrep module of Schrodinger suite 2021-4. The 2D structure of compounds was converted to 3D structures, energy was minimized and optimized for their geometry, desalted, and corrected for their chirality. The ligands A1-A9 were minimized using the OPLS-3 force field in Schrodinger suit-2021-4 until an RMSD of 2.0 Å° was achieved. A single low-energy ring confirmation per ligand was generated and the optimized ligands were used for docking analysis. Standard drugs were embedded into the generated grid of human PPAR γ protein to access their binding affinities.

IV) docking of the ligands

Using the G-module of the Schrodinger suite 2021-4 in extra precision (XP) mode docking was done using default parameters on the compounds prepared by the LigPrep module of the Schrodinger suite. The binding modes with the best G scores were selected.

Analysis of the docking studies

The XP visualizer of the Glide module was used to analyze the results of docking studies. The glide score of the compounds was compared with the glide score of the standard pioglitazone ^[24].

Prime MM-GB/SA studies

The ligand-receptor complex binding free energy and post-docking energy minimization were performed using prime molecular mechanics – generalized born surface area (MM-GB/SA) of Schrodinger 2021. The prime generalized-born/surface area (GB/SA) continuum solvent model was used to assess the relative enthalpy and entropy-associated components in the binding of the ligand-protein complex ^[25]. The formula used to calculate the energy contributions from molecular mechanics polar solvation and a nonpolar solvation factor in kilo calories is as follows:

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta G_{\text{complex}} - \Delta G_{\text{protein}} - \Delta G_{\text{ligand}}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \text{calculated binding free energy (complex)}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{complex}} = \text{Binding Free energy (minimized complex)}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{protein}} = \text{Binding Free energy (Receptor)}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{ligand}} = \text{Binding Free energy (unbound ligand)}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHEMISTRY

A total of nine compounds were synthesized and the percentage yields ranged from 62 to 88. The solvent system used for TLC was ethyl acetate and ether (4:6) and the R_f values were calculated, the FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}), ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ , ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ and Mass (ESI) spectral data were used to determine the structures of the compounds synthesized and are reported in the physicochemical data of the compounds.

Antioxidant Activity

The percentage scavenging activity of the compounds was calculated by the formula described in the above sections and the values were given in Table 1 and represented in the graphical form in Fig:1. The percentage scavenging of DPPH free radical and H_2O_2 free radical by the synthesized compounds was found to be in the range of 46 -79% and 45-78 % respectively. The compounds A3, A5, and A8 exhibited significant percentage inhibition, while the compounds A4 and A6 exhibited nearly equipotent activity when compared with the standard ascorbic acid by the DPPH free radical scavenging method. The percentage scavenging of the compounds A3, A4, A5, A6, and A8 showed significant antioxidant activity than the standard ascorbic acid by the H_2O_2 scavenging method.

Table 1: Antioxidant Activity by DPPH free Radical Scavenging Method and H_2O_2 scavenging method

S No:	COMPOUND (0.1mM)	% INHIBITION By DPPH method	% INHIBITION by H_2O_2 method
1	ASCORBIC ACID	77	71
2	A1	51	45
3	A2	54	52
4	A3	79	76
5	A4	73	78
6	A5	77	72
7	A6	79	77
8	A7	66	66
9	A8	78	76
10	A9	46	45
11	PIOGLITAZONE	61	61

Fig 1: Graphical representation of Antioxidant activity by DPPH free Radical Scavenging Method and H₂O₂ Scavenging Method***In silico* studies**

The *in silico* ADME properties of all molecules have been determined using QikProp Schrodinger Suite and have been reported in Table 6. The molecular weight of the molecules ranged from 281.328 to 472.56, the total solvent-accessible area 505.08 to 740.07, the donor hydrogen bonds were less than 2, the acceptor hydrogen bonds were ranging from 3 to 5, the QPlog P values ranged from 3.18 to 6.53, the QPlogS values ranged from -4.12 to -8.34 and the percent human oral absorption was found to be 100%. All the molecules designed followed Lipinski's Rule of Five and thus were more likely to be drug-like.

Table 3: QikProp ADME properties

S No:	Ligand	MW	SASA	Donor HB	Accept HB	QP logPo/w	QPlogS	Percent Human Oral Absorption	Rule of Five
1	A1	281.328	505.086	1	3	3.182	-4.128	100	0
2	A2	295.355	558.751	0	3	3.97	-4.951	100	0
3	A3	431.505	740.073	0	4.5	5.818	-6.892	100	1
4	A4	367.419	676.641	0	5	4.118	-5.589	100	0
5	A5	372.441	661.926	0	4.5	4.623	-5.737	100	0
6	A6	472.56	764.435	0	4.5	6.529	-8.341	100	1
7	A7	351.462	686.663	0	3	5.465	-6.665	100	1
8	A8	381.489	728.996	1	4.7	4.949	-6.39	100	0
9	A9	319.377	604.499	0.5	3	4.616	-5.642	100	0

Molecular Docking

The glide scores and binding free energies, prime MM-GB/SA binding free energies of the molecules were reported in Table 2. Fig 2 represents the 2D interactions of A2 at the active site. Hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic bonding, and polar interactions were observed mainly with the binding site residues, Phe 282, Cys 285, Gln 286, Arg 288, Ser 289, His 323, Ile 326, Tyr327, Leu330, Leu 333, Phe 363, Met 364, Ile 449.

Table 2: Glide XP Gscore Values (kcal/mol) and Prime MMGBSA binding free energy values (kcal/mol) in the active site of PPAR γ

S No:	COMPOUND	G SCORE	GLIDE ENERGY kcal/mol	MM-GB /SA BINDING ENERGY (kcal/mol)
1	A1	-9.3	-41.50	-56.16
2	A2	-9.3	-43.12	-61.29
3	A3	-6.2	-49.36	-63.74
4	A4	-5.3	-41.30	-55.21
5	A5	-5.8	-44.54	-65.68
6	A6	-7.6	-53.52	-106.52
7	A7	-5.8	-33.57	-55.66
8	A8	-6.6	-48.27	-79.71
9	A9	-5.9	-36.50	65.39
10	PIOGLITAZONE	-7.8	-50.59	-82.88

All the compounds showed *in silico* activity at the PPAR γ receptor with the G score ranging from -5.3 to -9.3 kcal/mol. The compound A6 showed a G score (-7.6 kcal/mol) equipotent to that of the G score of standard pioglitazone (-7.8 kcal/mol). Compounds A1 and A2 showed significant G score values (-9.3 & -9.3 kcal/mol) when compared to the G score of standard pioglitazone (-7.8 kcal/mol). The post-docking minimization revealed binding free energies (ΔG_{bind} values) in the range of -55.21 (A4) to -106.52 kcal/mol (A6). The highest binding energy at the PPAR γ receptor was shown by compound A6. The stability of the docking complex will be predicted by the MM-GB/SA scoring function.

Fig 2: 2D interaction of the compound A2 at the active site PPAR γ

The interaction of C=O of thiazolidinedione forming a hydrogen bond with the Gln 286 can be seen in fig 2.

Conclusion

Novel 5-([1,1-biphenyl]-4-yl)-2,4-thiazolidinediones were synthesized and evaluated for antioxidant and antidiabetic activities. Compounds with bulky substituents with methoxy [A3], alkoxy [A4], cyano [A6], pyridyl [A5], and hydroxy [A8] groups at the 3rd position showed significant antioxidant activity. All the molecules obeyed Lipinski's Rule of Five. From the molecular docking studies conducted at the PPAR γ active site, it was revealed that few compounds showed significant G scores at the active site than the standard, and from the prime MM-GB/SA binding energies it was confirmed that the compound A6 [ΔG -106.52 kcal/mol] showed significant binding affinity when compared with the standard pioglitazone.

Conflicts of interest

Authors declare no conflicts of interest to disclose

Compliance with ethical standards

This article does not contain any studies involving animals or human subjects

REFERENCES

1. Long N, Le Gresley A, Wren SP. Thiazolidinediones: an in-depth study of their synthesis and application to medicinal chemistry in the treatment of diabetes mellitus. *Chem Med Chem*. 2021;16(11):1716-35. doi: [10.1002/cmdc.202100177](https://doi.org/10.1002/cmdc.202100177), PMID [33844475](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33844475/).
2. Sucheta, Sumit Tahlan, Prabhakar Kumar Verma. Biological potential of thiazolidinedione derivatives of synthetic origin. *Chem. Cent. J.* 2017; 11:130 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13065-017-0357-2>.
3. Kharroubi AT, Darwish HM. Diabetes mellitus: the epidemic of the century. *World J Diabetes*. 2015; 25,6(6):850-67. doi: [10.4239/wjd.v6.i6.850](https://doi.org/10.4239/wjd.v6.i6.850), PMID [26131326](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26131326/).
4. Khan MAB, Hashim MJ, King JK, Govender RD, Mustafa H, Al Kaabi J. Epidemiology of Type 2 Diabetes - Global Burden of Disease and Forecasted Trends. *J Epidemiol Glob Health*. 2020 ;10(1):107-111. doi: [10.2991/jegh.k.191028.001](https://doi.org/10.2991/jegh.k.191028.001). PMID: [32175717](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32175717/); PMCID: [PMC7310804](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PMC7310804/).
5. Prabhakar PK. Pathophysiology of Secondary Complications of Diabetes Mellitus. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2016;9(1):32- 36.

6. P. Laxmi Madhuri, G. Rajitha. The Intriguing Thiazolidinediones as PPAR γ Agonists: A Review. *Int. J. Life Sci. Pharma Res.* 2023; 13(5):25-50. Doi:10.22376/ijlpr.2023.13.5 P25-P50
7. Lebovitz HE. Thiazolidinediones: the forgotten diabetes medications. *Curr Diab Rep.* 2019;19(12):151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-019-1270-y>.
8. Malhotra, M. et al., Synthesis, characterization and pharmacological evaluation of (Z)-2-(5 (biphenyl-4-yl) -3-(1- (imino) ethyl) -2,3 - dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) phenol derivatives as potent antimicrobial and antioxidant agents. *Arab. J. Chem.* 2013; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.01.005>.
9. Vithal M. Kulkarni Narsingh Sachan, Suresh Thareja, Ritesh Agarwal, Shivajirao S. Kadam; Substituted biphenyl ethanones as antidiabetic agents: synthesis and in-vivo screening. *Int.J. PharmTech Res.* 2009;1(4).
10. Katselou MG, Matralis AN, Kourounakis AP. Developing potential agents against atherosclerosis: Design, synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of novel dual inhibitors of oxidative stress and Squalene Synthase activity. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2017; 29(138): 748-760.
11. Sandeep Singh, P. Geeta R ramajayam. Isolation, synthesis and medicinal chemistry of biphenyl analogs – A review. *Results Chem.* 2023;6: 101135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2023.101135>.
12. Sohda T, Momose Y, Meguro K, Kawamatsu Y, Sugiyama Y, Ikeda H. Studies on antidiabetic agents. Synthesis and hypoglycemic activity of 5-[4-(pyridylalkoxy)benzyl]-2,4-thiazolidinediones. *Arzneimittel forschung.* 1990;40(1):37-42. PMID: 2339998.
13. Shubhanjali Shukla, Pankaj Kumar, Nirupam Das, N.S. Hari Narayana Moorthy, Sushant Kumar Shrivastava, Piyush Trivedi, Radhey Shyam Srivastava. Synthesis, Characterization, Biological Evaluation and Docking of Coumarin Coupled Thiazolidinedione Derivatives and its Bioisosteres as PPAR γ agonists. *Med. Chem.* 2012; 8: 834-845.
14. Ahmed, D.; Khan, M.; Saeed, R. Comparative Analysis of Phenolics, Flavonoids, and Antioxidant and Antibacterial Potential of Methanolic, Hexanoic and Aqueous Extracts from *Adiantum caudatum* Leaves. *Antioxid.* 2015; 4: 394–409. doi: 10.3390/antiox4020394.
15. Brand-Williams, W.; Cuvelier, M.E.; Berset, C. Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity. *LWT-Food Sci. Technol.* 1995; 28: 25–30.
16. Sambrajyam, J, Vidya Rani, M., Rajitha, G. Synthesis, Molecular Docking and Biological Evaluation of Naphthyl N-Acyl Hydrazone Derivatives. *Asian J. Chem.* 2022; 34(7): 1675–1682. <https://doi.org/10.14233/ajchem.2022.23632>.
17. T. Sarala Devi, G.Rajitha. Microwave Assisted Synthesis and Evaluation of N-cinnamoyl aryl hydrazones for Cytotoxic and Antioxidant Activities. *J. Chem.* 2016; 32(3):1703-1709.
18. Rajitha G, Nagalakshmi G, Varalakshmi K, Praneetha P. Synthesis and biological evaluation of novel Cinnamic acid derivatives for antibacterial and antioxidant activities. *International Journal of Chemical Science.* 2011;9:1811-1818.
19. Cheng F, Li W, Liu G, Tang Y. In silico ADMET prediction: recent advances, current challenges and future trends. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 2013;13(11):1273-89. doi: 10.2174/15680266113139990033. PMID: 23675935.

20. Rajitha G, Prasad KVSRG, Umamaheswari A, Prardhan D, Bharathi K. Synthesis, biological evaluation, and molecular docking studies of N- (α - acetamido cinnamoyl) aryl hydrazine derivatives as antiinflammatory and analgesic agents. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*. 2014;23:5204-5214.
21. Potlapati Varakumar, Kalirajan Rajagopal, Fahadul Islam, Kannan Raman, Gowramma Byran, et al., Identifying Potent 9-Anilinoacridine-Based HER2 Breast Cancer Inhibitors Using in Silico Computational Approaches. *J. Biol. Regul. Homeost. Agents*. 2023; 37(12): 6511–6523. <https://doi.org/10.23812/j.biol.regul.homeost.agents.20233712.616>.
22. Sasikala M, Rajitha G. (2019). Cytotoxic oxindole derivatives: in vitro EGFR inhibition, pharmacophore modeling, 3D-QSAR and molecular dynamics studies. *Journal of Receptors and Signal Transduction*, 2019;39(5-6), 1–10.
23. Lucia Fernanda C. da Costa Leite, Rosa Helena Veras Mourao, Maria do Carmo Alves de Lima, Suely Lins Galdino, Marcelo Zaldini Hernandez et al., Synthesis, biological evaluation and molecular modeling studies of arylidene-thiazolidinediones with potential hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic activities; *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 2007; 42: 1263e1271 doi:10.1016/j.ejmech.2007.02.015.
24. Álvarez-Almazán, S.; Navarrete-Vázquez, G.; Padilla-Martínez, I.I.; Correa-Basurto, J.; Alemán-González-Duhart, D.; Tamay-Cach, F.; Mendieta-Wejebe, J.E. A New Symmetrical Thiazolidinedione Derivative: In Silico Design, Synthesis, and In Vivo Evaluation on a Streptozotocin-Induced Rat Model of Diabetes. *Processes*. 2021; 9: 1294. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9081294>.
25. Rishabh Kharea, Kalirajan Rajgopalb, Kaveri prasad, Srikanth Jupudid, Preeya Negie, Jayanthi Koppulaf. Comparative binding pattern analysis of 5-MeO-DMT and 7-MeO-DMT against 5HT2A receptor employing molecular docking, MMGB-SA and molecular dynamics studies. *Eur. Chem. Bull.* 2023;12(5):5283-5291.